

Factors & Factors Influencing Mobile Learning Adoption In ware E-Learning: Case Study

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Abstract— This study analyses the challenges which Kuwait's national e-learning project faces when trying to implement mobile learning, or m-learning, successfully. With an emphasis on tablet distribution to teachers and students, the study looks at challenges and opportunities related to mobile learning. The study, which is specifically being carried out inside Kuwaiti higher education (HE) institutions, is to evaluate the views and reasons that students have for embracing m-learning, examine the effectiveness of the technology, and investigate social and gender concerns that may have an impact on its future growth. Statistical techniques like the analysis of variance (ANOVA) and independent-sample t-tests were used with a questionnaire given to 620 students. The results show differences in age and gender, which throws into focus social and cultural aspects that can prevent people from adopting mobile learning. A thorough examination of these problems yields insightful information for improving strategies.

Keywords: Mobile learning, Human-Computer Interaction, Gender differences Higher education, E-learning

Introduction-

Since most aspects of our daily existence now rely on mobile devices, mobile learning (m-learning) has become the term used to describe their use in educational programmers. This idea may be summed into a learning dynamic between students and the different resources they have access to, which are now available remotely because of technology advancements [1]. Young Arab students have embraced the use of such technologies to help with educational tasks [2]. The national e-learning plan proposed by Kuwait's Ministry of Education includes the provision of tablets to teachers and students for use in the classroom [3]. Sales of mobile technology are growing steadily in Kuwait & display no signs of abating [4]. With an excellent structure to facilitate its use & that follow accessibility, especially for younger generations, Kuwait is ideally positioned to take advantage of everything that mobile communication has to offer. Research indicates that mobile learning can foster creativity and support networking, information sharing, and the generation of new ideas [7, 8]. On the other hand, only a small number of tested educational apps have been shown to enhance intelligence and enhance learning outcomes.

The primary advantages of mobile learning, with an emphasis on speed, universality, interactions, privacy, merging, accessibility, and correspondence [9]. Despite all of the educational advantages that m-learning offers, Kuwait has not fully embraced this teaching approach. It's critical to comprehend the present roadblocks preventing Kuwait from successfully implementing, adopting, and rolling out mobile learning techniques.

While mobile HCI is concerned with the nuances of an individual's relationship with a system that is mobile [11, 12], human-computer interaction (HCI) is concerned with how individuals approach and manage their interactions with computers [10]. How different systems, offerings, and applications for mobile devices are used may be affected by cultural elements, which are all part of the specific dynamics. Personality, intellectual choice, age, gender, and prior usage of technology in social and educational contexts are significant user characteristics in this regard [13]. In order to optimize learning, educators and m-learning system developers would be well to modify their present settings to take gender disparities and a variety of social contexts into account [14, 15].

Gender is one of the many important aspects that influence how people use their mobile phones, but it's also important to realize that culture could play an equally important role. Previous research has shown that people's methods and habits while using technology are influenced by both gender and age. In spite of this, there is a dearth of research on the influence of individual characteristics on these behaviors in the context of mobile learning in Kuwait. By looking at these variables, we can create more

efficient plans and strategies that support each student in improving learning outcomes and academic programmers. Therefore, we believe it is crucial to evaluate learners' ideas and preferences about mobile education potential and utilization through a social and gender analysis in order to expedite adoption throughout Kuwait.

The research presented here aims to shed light on important factors that influence learners' m-learning behaviors and interactions. We investigate how learners understand the relevance of mobile learning in relation to their ages, genders, and social contexts. In doing so, we believe it is essential to understand the particulars by deepening our understanding of their perspectives on the potential benefits of mobile learning and raising our awareness of the obstacles that students encounter as a result of societal issues and issues with educational facilities. By examining the characteristics of learners and the social dynamics that influence their perceptions of the potential of mobile technology, this study adds to the current body of knowledge in mobile HCI. Additionally, it offers educational authorities a way to combine methods with the social and personal struggles that students face in order to make even greater use of m-learning apps.

knowledge by examining the characteristics of the learners and the social variables that influence how they view the possibilities of mobile technology. Additionally, it offers educational leaders a way to integrate methods with the social and personal struggles that students encounter, allowing them to make even greater use of m-learning apps. The opportunity to investigate how attitudes and viewpoints about mobile learning evolved as a result served as the impetus for this study. It also measures the efficacy of the technology, looks at elements linked to age and gender, and considers potential social and cultural influences.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the following questions: • Does the use of social media by learners depend on any significant gender factors?

1. Do significant age differences have an impact on how students use social media?
2. Does the impression of m-learning by learners depend on any significant gender factors?
3. Do significant age disparities have an impact on how learners see mobile learning?

The remaining parts are organized as follows: The related research on students' perceptions of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) across various nations and academic areas are included in Section 2. The approach is presented in the third part. Experimental samples and assessment standards are described in depth. Section 4 presents the findings, and Section 5 discusses the findings. Section 6 concludes with recommendations for further work.

Related Work

An examination of the connections between users and the mobile technology they use on a daily basis is known as mobile human-computer interaction [20, 12]. As Ref. [9] explains, for businesses developing mobile technology, the user interface is a top priority. Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) provides information on stable interaction between different devices. An additional investigation examined the viewpoints and attitudes of English majors resulting from their time at Kuwait's College of Education [21]. According to their research, the majority of students (80.3%) knew how mobile technology may be used to improve the classroom. Furthermore, they believed that having access to m-learning had enhanced their vocabulary and grammatical skills. Additionally, survey study was done by Ref. [1] to determine the possibility of m-learning and higher learning (HE) facilities integrating in Saudi Arabia. Their results demonstrate the potential that m-learning offers that cannot be obtained through other means, leading to advancements in education because of improved study techniques and knowledge gains. Additionally, Ref. [22] investigated how Saudi female higher education lecturers used mobile technologies. The findings demonstrated that recognizing social structures and avoiding adjusting to new technologies are crucial for directing subsequent actions towards m-learning. Comparable studies conducted by Ref. [23] examined students' opinions towards mobile learning in Saudi Arabian higher education institutions. They used quantitative approaches to finish a survey that was completed by eighty HE students.

Ref. [24] conducted research that examined how students utilize cell phones for assignments. At Finland's Lahti College of Applied Sciences, data were collected from 77 students. They emphasized how adding mobile learning (m-learning) to coursework tends to make students very happy and gives them an additional incentive to study. An additional study conducted by Reference [25] aimed to examine how students view mobile technology as the best tool for customising and improving their experiences when not in the classroom. These results, which demonstrate how m-learning may enable new learning experiences, boosting learning capacity, and inspiring learners to pursue their efforts in their leisure time, were compiled by fifty-three graduate pupils from a Southern US University. The goal of Ref.

[26]'s study was to describe how various social groups employ m-learning. According to the study's findings, m-learning gives refugees access to knowledge.

Additionally, the study by Ref. [27] looked at how students felt about the effectiveness of mobile learning. According to the results of a poll conducted among Indian higher education institutions with 100 students, the majority of students believe that mobile learning is crucial to their academic endeavours. Additionally, by examining socio-cultural elements that influence access to and use of technology for learning, Ref. [28] investigated students' views about using mobile phones for studying. They discovered that as a result, students' excitement and optimism for individual as well as collaborative learning increased.

Gender and cultural Difference on mobile HCI

In terms of gender, a number of studies have examined the differences in mobile technology use among male and female students as well as the inclusion of national and cultural variables. For instance, the study of Ref. [29] examined the responses of 90 New Zealand students to a short messaging service (SMS) and examined how both male & female students responded to it. Their research reveals significant differences in application and intent, but no such differences were discovered in terms of usability or individual technological competency. Ref. [30] also emphasizes gender differences found through a cross-national analysis of mobile apps, use the USA, the nation of Sweden, Korea, & Japan etc as examples. Data was evaluated in relation to context management, networking, accessibility, and correspondence problems.

The results address a number of attitude- and gender-related concerns. But there are hints that suggest the main problem is cultural. Comparably, the findings of Reference [12] showed minimal variations in the motivation and satisfaction levels of male and female students when it came to their usage of e-learning. Cultural differences in views and attitudes towards technology may be quite important in determining how it is adopted and used in daily life and in learning [31, 32, 17]. As a prime example, several research focused on Saudi Arabia, where gender stereotypes are strongly influenced by cultural elements [33, 34]. Analyzing the disparities among male and female Instagram users, Ref. [35] also sought to determine the influence that cultural variables have on the platform's use in Kuwait. Ladies from carrying out.

Methodology

Numerous studies have been conducted to find out how students feel about mobile learning. In order to collect pertinent data on the experimental sample for these kinds of studies, a questionnaire is utilized, and the statistical technique is then applied to ascertain the importance of the result. An online survey & Analyses of Variance (ANOVA) were used to investigate the effects of age, gender-related characteristics, social and cultural concerns, and other variables that may have affected the use of m-learning in Kuwait. If there's any significant variations between the independent variables, such age and gender, the one-way ANOVA can be used to find them.

Evaluation instrument

An online questionnaire was created based on a number of earlier researches [21, 36, 3]. Most importantly, the measuring scales and the questions asked were tailored to be unique to this study. The questionnaire is divided into three pieces. The essential student data, such age and gender, are gathered in Section 1. The second section investigates how frequently students utilize different social media platforms. This is done by utilizing the four rating systems of "Always," "Sometimes," "Rare," and "I don't use it." Gender and age were considered significant variables: Part 3 focuses on the attitudes and actions of students about the use of social media and mobile technologies. This portion consists of the following eight questions, each of which uses a Fifth Point Likert scale: 1 denotes a strong disagreement, 2 disagreements, 3 neutrality, 4 agreement, and 5 strong agreement. The initial three questions examine learners' perceptions of mobile learning, as the tables 4 and 5 demonstrate. Inquiries four and five go into their viewpoints on the adaptability of social media in their educational process. Lastly, the final three questions look at social and cultural aspects that influence the use of social media and m-learning. Twenty students participated in a pilot study that was conducted in advance of the main investigation.

This was finished to determine the feasibility of the study, work out any kinks, refine the questions as needed, and determine whether the findings provided the necessary information. Some questions were therefore reworded to make them clearer. Using SPSS, the validity of the questionnaire was verified by calculating Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's

Alpha has a total value of (0.92). The results are reliable, and the questionnaire may be used to the larger research group.

An independent-sample t-test and a test of variance (ANOVA) have been used as statistical techniques. The latter is necessary to determine whether there is statistical significance among two unrelated groups (the two independent variables being male and female). When comparing more than one group and variables, One-Way ANOVA can be used to provide contrasts with means that have statistical significance (the three age groups being the independent variables). Since the data is parametric, the t-test and ANOVA have been selected based on how well they apply to interval scale characteristics. For each example, a level of significance of 0.05 was chosen, and statistical analysis was used to make sure that the variable assessments were objective.

Sample

All participants in this study were students enrolled in various higher education institutions in Kuwait, chosen to represent the private as well as public sectors. After the lines of contact were established, 620 respondents—a mix of males and females—were chosen at random to complete the online survey. The authors of the study, who are associated to both public as well as private universities in Kuwait, managed the online dissemination using social media and email. One week following the initial roll-out, responses were collected via the Poll Monkey programmer for evaluation. There were 339 female and 160 male replies out of the total 479 legitimate responses that were acknowledged and used in the statistical analysis.

Result

There were 336 responses in the 16–24 age range, 116 within the 25–35 age category, and 47 older than 35 in the age range that was represented. Using statistical analysis, the discrepancies among the variables were examined objectively.

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Age</i>			<i>Total</i>
	16-24	25-35	More Than 36	
Female	218	80	41	339
Male	118	36	6	160
Total	336	116	47	499

Table 1. Students' Gender and Age

Frequent usage of social media by students The second section of the survey investigates how frequently learners access social media, especially through well-known platforms including Snap chat, Instagram, Face book, YouTube, LinkedIn, and Twitter. By looking over the answers, we were able to find any noteworthy variations in the way these apps are used. The gender and age findings are listed in Table 2, and Table 3, respectively. Using a t-test, Table 2's gender-related results demonstrate that there is no discernible difference between Twitter's "significance level" ($p=0.113$) and Instagram ($p=0.487$). The other social networking apps, however, do record Face book ($p=0.000$), Snap chat ($p=0.010$), YouTube ($p=0.001$), and LinkedIn ($p=0.000$) all showed significant differences. Furthermore, by examining the mean values, we discover that males are more likely than women to make use of Face book, YouTube, and LinkedIn, whereas women use Snap chat more frequently.

Making Use of One-Way Table 3 results, which show no significant differences between the three age groups for the social media apps Tweet ($p=0.443$), Insta ($p=0.248$), and LinkedIn ($p=0.124$), may be evaluated using ANOVA. Conversely, the findings indicate that there are notable distinctions amongst the other major social media platforms, which are Twitter ($p=0.006$), YouTube ($p=0.017$), and Snap ($p=0.000$). However, the findings also show that none of all three age groups are very enthusiastic with Face book. Nonetheless, the younger generation seems to be gravitating towards Snap chat and YouTube.

The following results are obtained when the medians are sorted from highest to lowest, regardless of the years of age and gender of the respondents: YouTube, are among those Snap chat, a social Face book, Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn

List of Social Media	Parameters							
	Gender	Always	Sometime	Rare	Do Not use	Mean	SD	Sig
LinkedIn	Male	4	12	9	135	1.28	.711	0.000
	Female	2	8	19	310	1.12	1435	
YouTube	Male	112	41	6	1	3.65	.585	0.001
	Female	193	121	18	7	3.47	.693	
Facebook	Male	14	17	33	96	1.68	.980	0.000
	Female	13	23	40	263	1.37	.775	
Instagram	Male	76	57	16	11	3.24	.894	0.487
	Female	148	133	39	19	3.21	.857	
Snapchat	Male	101	22	15	22	3.26	1.102	0.010
	Female	253	37	8	41	3.48	1.013	
Twitter	Male	47	50	31	32	2.70	1.098	0.133
	Female	93	95	63	88	2.57	1.148	

Table 2. Analyzing Gender-Specific Trends in Learners' Social Media Usage

List of Social Media	Parameters							
	Age	Always	Sometimes	Rare	Do not use	Mean	SD	Sig.
LinkedIn	16-24	4	9	17	306	1.14	.496	.124
	25-35	2	8	8	98	1.26	.661	
	>35	0	3	3	41	1.19	.537	
YouTube	16-24	215	102	15	4	3.57	.638	.017
	25-35	69	40	5	2	3.52	.666	
	> 35	21	20	4	2	3.28	.800	
Facebook	16-24	12	25	51	248	1.41	.779	.006
	25-35	8	10	14	84	1.50	.918	
	>35	7	5	8	27	1.83	1.129	
Instagram	16-24	145	136	38	17	3.22	.838	.248
	25-35	62	34	12	8	3.29	.914	
	> 35	17	20	5	5	3.04	.955	
Snapchat	16-24	255	37	12	32	3.53	.946	.000
	25-35	81	12	7	16	3.36	1.091	
	> 35	18	10	4	15	2.66	1.290	
Twitter	16-24	98	96	67	75	2.65	1.123	.443
	25-35	31	36	19	30	2.59	1.143	
	>35	11	13	8	15	2.43	1.175	

Table 3. Analyzing Age Different in Learners' Social Media Usage

Learners m-learning perspectives

The third component of the questionnaire centers on the views and attitudes of the learners on mobile learning. Tables 4 and 5 present the replies of the learners with respect to gender and age, respectively. Table 4's results, which were obtained using a t-test, show that there are no gender-specific variations in perceptions of the advantages of social media apps or m-learning. The analysis of the average scores for questions 1 to 5 reveals that learners have a favorable view of the potential of mobile learning, with no gender variation.

Proceeding to Topics 6, 7, and 8, we may examine the perspectives of students about the social and cultural elements impacting mobile learning and social media usage. Considering the ability of male and female students to communicate with one another using m-learning technologies, Question 6's results show a neutral stance. Males score higher (3.09) as females (2.96) among people who do express rejection. As for Question 7, "Will society reject mobile learning because of customs and traditions?," the answer is also in the neutral zone. In contrast, female viewpoints are demonstrated to be greater (2.90 against 2.82) when comparing those of men and women. Furthermore, the results were inconclusive when it came to the topic of if social media applications would be detrimental to family life. Once more, lady.

Sr No	Question Summary	Parameters								
		Gender	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	SD	Sig.
Q1	M-learning increases students' and instructors' interactions	Male	63	57	30	4	6	4.04	1.012	.581
		Female	120	135	54	22	8	3.99	.994	
Q2	I reject m-learning if it allows male and female students to contact each other	Male	28	30	55	22	25	3.09	1.286	.586
		Female	46	65	106	75	47	2.96	1.230	
Q3	The use of social media will cause social and family problems	Male	21	39	52	30	18	3.09	1.186	.890
		Female	54	97	110	56	22	3.31	1.121	
Q4	Our society will reject m-learning because of our customs and traditions	Male	12	34	57	27	30	2.82	1.186	.701
		Female	37	63	110	87	42	2.90	1.170	
Q5	Learning by mobile increases students' motivation	Male	42	46	49	16	7	3.63	1.109	.885
		Female	85	104	91	48	11	3.60	1.106	
Q6	Social media applications help in educational attainment	Male	49	67	30	8	6	3.91	1.014	.168
		Female	70	153	65	40	11	3.68	1.031	
Q7	Social media helps to strengthen communication	Male	72	57	19	3	9	4.13	1.068	.184

	with instructors and students	Female	134	143	35	20	7	4.11	.954	
Q8	I believe that learning by mobile is a great idea	Male	47	50	40	12	11	3.69	1.172	.773
		Female	97	111	77	38	16	3.69	1.138	

Table 4. Analyzing student Perceptions of M-Learning t-test

In evaluating the age-related results, an A single direction ANOVA analysis of variance on questions 1–6 (as shown in Table 5) reveals no statistically significant variations in the capability for m-learning or the use of social media. We may conclude from a review of the mean values obtained that learners' favorable perceptions on the practicality of m-learning are not significantly influenced by their age.

However, when we look at Question 7 and 8, that display the age group's varying replies, distinctions do become apparent. A neutral response was noted for Question 7, which queried whether cultural customs would prevent access to m-learning. The mean score for persons over 35 was 3.32, which was somewhat higher than the scores for the lower age groups. In addition, Question Eight others had no opinion about social media causing problems in the family. But the findings indicate more agreement among older persons, having a mean of 3.62 for those over 35 and 3.53 for those between 25 and 35 years old, as opposed to 3.09 for those between 16 and 24 years old.

	Questions	Age	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	SD	Sig.
Q1	I reject m-learning if it allows male and female students to contact each other	16–24	53	60	117	61	45	3.04	1.237	.327
		25–35	14	21	35	26	20	2.85	1.253	
		> 35	7	14	9	10	7	3.09	1.316	
Q2	Social media helps to strengthen communication with instructors and students	16–24	146	128	39	14	9	4.15	.968	.144
		25–35	49	46	9	9	3	4.11	1.020	
		> 35	11	26	6	0	4	3.85	1.063	
Q3	Learning by mobile increases students' motivation	16–24	90	93	101	41	11	3.63	1.102	.404
		25–35	31	38	28	13	6	3.65	1.144	
		> 35	6	19	11	10	1	3.40	1.035	
Q4	I believe that learning by mobile is a great idea	16–24	102	105	84	29	16	3.74	1.124	.084
		25–35	35	38	23	13	7	3.70	1.188	
		> 35	7	18	10	8	4	3.34	1.185	
Q5	Our society will reject m-learning because of our customs and traditions	16–24	32	63	111	77	53	2.83	1.185	.023
		25–35	7	23	43	27	16	2.81	1.095	
		> 35	10	11	13	10	3	3.32	1.218	

Q6	The use of social media will cause social and family problems	16–24	37	85	116	66	32	3.09	1.126	.000
		25–35	28	32	37	12	7	3.53	1.145	
		> 35	10	19	9	8	1	3.62	1.074	
Q7	M-learning increases students' and instructors' interactions	16–24	134	119	60	14	9	4.06	.992	.062
		25–35	42	49	17	6	2	4.06	.935	
		> 35	7	24	7	6	3	3.55	1.100	
Q8	Social media applications help in educational attainment	16–24	80	149	73	25	9	3.79	.976	.071
		25–35	30	53	15	13	5	3.78	1.088	
		> 35	9	18	7	10	3	3.43	1.211	

Table 5. Analyzing student Perceptions of M-Learning Age Different in t-test

Conclusion and Future Directions

The characteristics of its users, such as their age and gender, cognitive capacity, personality, and capacity for learning, are reflected in mobile HCI. The qualities of a learner may influence how they perceive and feel about the social use of mobile learning. The aim of this study is to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of learners' viewpoints and attitudes towards mobile learning by examining the associated social aspects and gender dynamics that exist in Kuwaiti facilities. By examining the important characteristics and social aspects of students that influence how they approach learning with mobile technology, the findings contribute to our knowledge of mobile HCI. The findings show that most students have a good opinion of this technique because of its flexibility in both time and place, which is not limited by age or gender.

Despite this good news, students exercise caution because of m-learning and social media use, which may lead to more communication between them. The results of the investigation do, however, indicate that younger pupils exhibited less caution. Thus, as Kuwait develops further, future generations may adopt and adopt distinct perspectives about mobile learning. The data also demonstrate significant gender and age inequalities, providing evidence that social and cultural variables impede the use of m-learning. Thus, in this particular setting, our study contributes to the body of knowledge about gender dynamics. Having a deeper understanding of the problems at hand might help develop more effective plans for helping pupils use better learning techniques.

Education professionals may already be familiar with m-learning, but they might still benefit from updating their lesson plans to take into account social dynamics and gender dynamics in order to make them more applicable to all students who use mobile devices. Every student's strategy will continue to depend on how well-connected they are to mobile devices. This means that educators who want to improve their methods of instruction by integrating mobile technology even further must do it in a way that takes into account social constraints and gender-specific cultural dynamics. mobile learning continues to be in its infancy when it comes as Kuwaiti educational institutions are concerned.

To assist their pupils succeed despite elements connected to cultural and social concerns or reliance on old traditions, professionals and the policymakers who support them should improve techniques and environments with the necessary understanding and respect of the obstacles involved. The results indicate specific social and cultural elements that may prove to be challenges for m-learning, in addition to age and gender discrepancies. In terms of potential future research, we suggest delving deeper into additional cultural and societal aspects that may prevent people from realising the promise of mobile learning and generate recommendations for educational experts and product developers. Detailed analysis of students' diverse qualities might result in several innovations regarding the ways in which m-learning can be facilitated.

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